

Family Conflict And Adolescents' Behaviour In Ondo City, Ondo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The family plays a vital role in supporting the growth and development of children. Family conflicts are believed to have both internal and external influences on adolescents' behavior and activities. However, in Ondo city, more studies need to be conducted on family conflict in relation to adolescents' behaviour. It is on this premise that the current paper appraises the relationship between family conflicts and adolescents' behaviour in Ondo State, with specific focus on adolescents' level of truancy and self-esteem. The study employed a descriptive research design. The Family Conflicts and Adolescents Behaviour questionnaire (FCABQ) comprising 33 items was administered to two hundred (200) adolescents within Ondo City to elicit data for the descriptive and inferential analysis of the research questions and hypotheses respectively. Data collected were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Findings of the first hypothesis revealed that there is a weak significant relationship between truancy and family conflicts among adolescents in Ondo City ($r = .262, p < 0.05$). The second hypothesis showed that there is no significant relationship between family conflicts and self-esteem among ($r = .124, p > 0.05$). Hypothesis three revealed that no significant difference exists between male and female adolescents affected by family conflict ($t = .643, p > 0.05$). This hypothesis is therefore accepted. The study recommended parental modelling, parental commitment and counselling programmes for adolescents to discourage truancy behaviour and boost their self-esteem positively.

Keywords: Family conflict; Truancy; Adolescents; Self-esteem.

INTRODUCTION

The family plays a crucial role in nurturing the growth and development of children. The family is a primary socialization agent which is considered to be a very important factor in influencing a child's development (Ozcinar, 2006). Family cohesions and relationships between members of the family play a significant role in the adjustment issues associated with the period of adolescence (Werner, 2003). Parents and every member of the family have always been the most important support system available to the child. A child's relationship with his/her parents is the strongest factor in moulding a child's personality or behaviour. However, no matter how loving a family is, all families go through some moments of disagreement or conflict. Malek (2013) opined that family conflict is any conflict that occurs within a family; between husbands and wives, parents and children, between siblings, or with extended families such as grandparents, aunts and uncles

The family serves as a child's primary foundation for protection, emotional support, education, and social development. Parents pass down values, attitudes, beliefs, rituals, and behaviors that have been shaped over generations. However, family dynamics can influence truancy, particularly when parents

are unavailable to meet their children's basic needs or adequately supervise their activities. Cumming and Deies, 2010 reported that risky families are characterized by conflict and aggression and by cold, unsupportive, and neglectful relationships. Emotional and behavioural issues such as anxiety, depression low self-esteem, disobedience, poor school attendance are some of the challenges that adolescents who witness violence constantly experience

Research suggests that family conflict is directly associated with adolescents' feelings of insecurity, aggressive behavior, conduct disorders, and psychological stress (Dunkle, Fondacaro, & Pathak, 1998; Wissink, Dekovic, & Meijer, 2006). According to Ngozi et al. (2013), the impact of parental conflict differs significantly between male and female adolescents, as shown in their study on the influence of parental conflict on adolescents' psychosocial adjustment in Nigeria.

Onongha (2020) conducted a study on family type and truancy behavior among 150 secondary school students in Oriade Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria. Using the Truancy Behavior Questionnaire (TBQ) to gather data, the analysis was carried out with ANOVA and T-tests. Among the findings, the study revealed no significant differences in truancy behavior among secondary school students, regardless of their family type.

Zhang et al. (2007) identified four primary categories of factors contributing to truancy among students: family factors, school factors, economic influences, and student-specific factors. Family-related causes of truancy include family type, parents' level of education, parental supervision, and household income. Similarly, Tenibiaje (2009), as cited in Onongha (2020), emphasized that the type of home a student comes from significantly impacts their academic performance, mental well-being, and likelihood of engaging in truant behavior.

Adolescents are more likely than younger children to exhibit internalizing behaviors in response to inter-parental conflict. Family conflict, which can manifest as verbal, physical, sexual, financial, or psychological disputes, often leads to unhealthy behaviors, poor attachment styles, and difficulties in interpersonal relationships. Common family issues, such as bickering, giving the cold shoulder, or eye-rolling, can contribute to mental health challenges for children, including depression, anxiety, poor sleep, and aggression. Musick and Meier (2010) observed that family conflicts impact boys directly through their coping behaviors, while for girls, the effects are indirect, mediated by threat appraisals and self-blame. This suggests that boys and girls adapt psychologically to family conflicts in different ways.

Exposure to interparental conflict is a significant source of stress for children and has been recognized as a major contributor to behavioral problems. Sana (2013), in a study on *Perceived Interparental Conflicts and Family Functioning as Predictors of Adjustment Problems in Late Adolescence*, found a strong positive correlation between inter-parental conflict and adjustment issues such as anger, antisocial behavior, and emotional distress. Similarly, Kim et al. (2008) observed that adolescents exposed to interparental conflict are more likely to experience relational and sexual aggression, verbal, emotional, and physical abuse, as well as hostile behaviors. Fear (2007), in a study on children of depressed parents, focused on inter-parental conflict, self-blame, and coping. The findings indicated that high levels of inter-parental conflict are closely linked to increased anxiety and aggressive behavior problems in children.

Statement of the problem

Family conflict can have profound effects on children, and prolonged exposure may lead to psychological harm. Adolescents, in particular, are vulnerable to the negative impacts of family issues, such as frequent parental fighting. Some may respond by displaying increased aggression, defiance, or other behavioral problems. Others might experience depressive symptoms, such as sadness, loneliness, or prolonged isolation. Adolescents exposed to parental conflict often feel anxious or torn in their loyalty between parents. This exposure increases the likelihood of emotional, social, and behavioral challenges, including lower academic performance and difficulties with concentration. Family conflict has long been linked to an increased risk of adjustment problems in children (Cummings & Davies, 2010). Higher levels of conflict within the family are associated with a rise in adolescents' symptoms of depression, anxiety, low self-esteem, aggressive behaviors, and other physical issues over time. Frequent and intense parental conflict can negatively impact a child's sense of safety and security, affecting their relationships with both parents and peers. Adolescents exposed

to parental conflict are more likely to experience unhealthy peer relationships, poor academic performance, low self-confidence, and a range of physical and mental health problems, including depression, anxiety, and violent behavior.

Family conflict, including both inter-parental and parent-adolescent conflict, plays a significant role in adolescents' emotional distress. Adolescents exposed to high levels of marital conflict, compared to those from non-conflictual families, tend to experience much higher levels of emotional difficulties over time (Gerard et al., 2006).

Purpose of the study

The main objective of this study seeks to find out the relationship between family conflict and adolescent behaviour in Ondo City, Ondo state, Nigeria.

The specific objectives are;

1. To determine the relationship between family conflict and truancy among adolescents in Ondo City, Ondo state, Nigeria
2. To examine the relationship between family conflict and self-esteem among adolescents in Ondo City, Ondo state, Nigeria
3. To establish whether it is the male or female adolescents who are more affected by conflicts in families

Limitation

Family conflict affects all members in various ways, but this study focused specifically on its impact on adolescents' behavior in Ondo City, Ondo State, located in the South-Western region of Nigeria. Future research could expand to include primary and tertiary institutions across the country.

Research Questions

1. What relationship exists between family conflict and truancy among adolescents?
2. What relationship exists between family conflict and self-esteem among adolescents?
3. What relationship exists between male and female adolescents affected by family conflicts?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between family conflict and truancy among adolescents.
2. There is no significant relationship between family conflict and adolescents' self-esteem.
3. There is no significant relationship between male and female adolescents affected by family conflict.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design for this study is a descriptive survey research design. This concerns the findings, describing and interpreting phenomena. As a quantitative research according to Danial (2004) it implies the collection of numerical data that are analyzed using a mathematically based method (a statistical method).

Population

The target population for this study consists of all adolescents in Senior Secondary schools within Ondo metropolis in Nigeria. However the study sampled only 200 adolescents in public and private secondary schools in Ondo metropolis.

Sampling and sampling techniques

The sample is taken as a portion of the population from many to represent and generalize the whole. The sample of this research work is calculated by using the Taro Yamane formula (Yamane (1973). Where a total of 200 respondents were computed to be the samples used to conduct this research.

Research Instrument

The instrument used for this study is a questionnaire that contained two parts; part 1 and part 2. Part one contains questions related to demographic information, while part 2 contains thirty (30) items related to the variables of adolescents' behaviour and family conflicts as used in this study.

Validity of the Instrument

The face and content validity of the self-structured questionnaire were assessed by two experts: an experienced statistician and a guidance counselor. Their feedback and suggestions led to revisions of the items, and the modified version was then retained and administered to the sampled respondents.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of an instrument refers to the degree to which it consistently measures what it is intended to measure. To assess the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted with fifty students. The reliability was then estimated using the scores obtained from the pilot test. Using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation, the overall coefficient value was found to be 0.82, indicating that the instrument is highly reliable.

Procedure for Data Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 21). The results were presented in frequency distribution tables with corresponding percentages. To conduct the inferential analysis, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and T-test statistics were applied, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

DATA ANALYSES

This section presents the results of data obtained from the respondents in frequency and percentages. Distribution of respondents by gender, age and parental economic status.

n = 200

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	115	57.5
Female	85	42.5
Age		
10 – 12	60	30.0
13 – 15	85	42.5
16 – 19	55	27.5
Parental Economic Status		
High	125	62.5
Average	75	37.5
Low	0	0.0

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between family conflict and truancy among adolescents.

Variables	Number N	Mean X	Standard Deviation SD	R	Sig.p	Remark
Family conflicts	200	18.10	5.17	.262	.000	significant
Truancy	200	20.88	3.42			

Result from the table above shows that the r calculated of 0.262 depicts that there is a weak relationship between truancy and family conflicts among adolescents in Ondo state. This is however, significant at 5% level of significance ($p < 0.05$). It therefore shows that there is a weak significant relationship between truancy and family conflicts among adolescents. The null hypothesis stated is therefore rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between family conflict and adolescents' self-esteem.

Variables	Number N	Mean X	Standard Deviation SD	R	Sig.p	Remark
Family conflicts	200	18.10	5.17	.124	.081	Not significant
Self – esteem	200	29.73	2.87			

Result from the table above shows that the r calculated of 0.124 depicts that there is no relationship between family conflicts and self - esteem among adolescents in Ondo state. This is however not significant at the 5% level of significance ($p > 0.05$). It therefore shows that there is no significant relationship between family conflicts and self - esteem among adolescents. The null hypothesis stated is therefore accepted.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference between male and female adolescents affected by family conflict.

Variables FAMILY CONFLICTS	Number N	Mean X	Standard Deviation SD	df	t. tab	t. cal	Sig.p	Remark
Male	115	18.04	5.24	198	1.9 8	.64 3	.858	Not significant
Female	85	18.17	5.11					

The table above presents the difference in adolescents based on gender with respect to their family conflicts. Its findings reveal that t.cal. of (.643) is less than the table value of (1.98). Similarly, the p-value of (.858) is greater than the significant level of (0.05), this depicts that the hypothesis is not significant hence the null hypothesis which states that no significant difference between male and female adolescents affected by family conflict is therefore accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Hypothesis one posits that there is no significant relationship between family conflict and truancy among adolescents. The findings showed a weak but significant relationship between truancy and family conflict. This aligns with the work of Onongha (2020), which revealed that family type does not determine the extent of truancy behavior among secondary school students.

Hypothesis two posits that there is no significant relationship between family conflict and adolescents' self-esteem. However, this study contrasts with the findings of Muthuri, Marete and Mburugu (2019), who reported that parental conflicts negatively impact self-esteem by lowering it. In contrast to the current findings, Cummings and Davies (2010) also noted that adolescents who witness family violence face an increased risk of emotional and behavioral problems, including anxiety, depression, poor school attendance and performance, low self-esteem, disobedience, nightmares, and physical health complaints.

Hypothesis three posits that there is no significant relationship between male and female adolescents affected by family conflict. However, the findings do not align with the work of Musick and Meier (2010), who stated that family conflicts directly impact boys through their coping behaviors, while girls are affected indirectly through threat appraisals and self-blame. They also noted that the psychological adaptation to family conflict differs between boys and girls. Additionally, this study contradicts the findings of Ngozi *et al.* (2013), which revealed that male and female adolescents show different social adjustments during parental conflicts.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it was revealed that there is a significant relationship between family conflict and truancy; however, there was no significant relationship between family conflict and adolescents' self-esteem, and no significant difference between male and female adolescents affected by family conflict. The following recommendations are made based on these findings:

1. Parents should model the behaviors they wish to see in their adolescents, as this will help discourage truancy and positively boost their self-esteem.
2. Parents should show greater commitment to their children's education to help prevent truancy.
3. Families experiencing conflict should consider seeking counseling promptly to avoid negative impacts on adolescents that may lead to behavioral problems.
4. Officials from the Ministry of Education should provide regular supervision and monitoring to enhance the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process, thereby reducing truancy among secondary school students.

5. Every school should employ a school counselor to whom students can turn for support and assistance.

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